

DACEM
Digitising Academic Catalogues for Enhanced Mobility

DACEM Technical Architecture for CCs

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

This document is intended to identify the most appropriate components and technologies for the development of the CC solution. This will constitute the technical architecture establishing how the different components will be interconnected and integrated.

The main purpose of this document is to facilitate the understanding of the technologies involved in the CC solution, so they can be adopted and extended by interested implementers, specifically Higher Education Institution (HEIs). A modular approach will be followed to enable whether the whole adoption of the complete solution or the partial adoption of specific components.

1.2. Document scope

This document focuses on the technologies and the main software components of the architecture for the CC solution. Particularly, it is of interest how the different components that can be developed can be integrated and managed.

Issues regarding the design of the user interface, the data models in the data base or specific programming solutions are out of the scope of this document.

1.3. Target audience

The intended audience of this document is mainly the technical people involved in the development of the CC software. This includes users that can be interested in the use of specific components of the solution and not the whole CC.

The document is also of interest for those involved in the deployment of the CC solution on their own premisses.

2. General consideration for choosing a technology stack

The CC solution should be provided in two different configurations:

- The CC solution can keep the information of a single HEI.
- The CC solution can be used to keep the information of several HEI. A typical example could be to provide the CC of the HEIs involved in a European University Alliance (EUA). In any case, it could be used to provide a joint course display for any kind of HEIs' association.

In addition, the CC should be available for its deployment in the premises of a HEI or in some third-party cloud provider.

2.1. Goal of the CC Solution

The goal of the CC solution is to support authenticated end-users, mainly HEI staff providing information that should be kept in the HEI CC and non-authenticated users, mainly students but also any kind of interested user, to browse and search the information available in the CC. By exposing the data in

machine readable formats via APIs, the solution should also enable external systems to leverage the stored course data.

2.2. Users

The following end-users are identified in the CC application:

- **General administrator.** This will be responsible for general configuration of the CC installation, including the management of institutions and users. It will also be able to create different temporal versions of the CC and manage their visibility for the different users.
- **HEI administrator.** Each institution in the CC installation should have a single administrator. This will be allowed to manage the main entities and users in the CC institution: programmes, users, organizational units, campuses, etc.
- **Organizational Unit/Programme administrator.** This will be responsible for the management of the organizational unit or specific programmes, including Individual Educational Components (IECs) and users.
- **Editor.** This role will be responsible for the information contained in specific entities of the CC. Some entities available will be: General Information, Resources and Services, Programme, Individual Educational Component, Campus, Organizational Unit.
- **Validator.** This role will be responsible for checking and validating the information available in the CC installation.
- **Non-authenticated users.** This role represents any person that visits the CC. The main role will be students, but it can be any person. This role will be allowed to browse and search the CC information freely.

2.3. Main user stories

- AS AN non-authenticated user (e.g. student) I WANT TO browse HEIs' CCs SO THAT I can locate the information of interest.
- AS AN non-authenticated user (e.g. student) I WANT to search HEIs' CCs SO THAT I can locate the information of interest.
- AS AN non-authenticated user (e.g. student) I WANT to see the information in the CC SO THAT I can decide where to study
- AS A Student I WANT to clearly identify and browse the subjects that can be done in a Erasmus stay SO THAT I don't get confused looking for subjects that are not available for me.
- Create programmes, configurations, ...
- Create IEC (Subjects)
- AS A HEI administrator I WANT TO assign editors and validators for specific sections of the HEI's CC SO THAT they can do their tasks in a controlled way
- AS A Programme administrator I WANT TO assign editors and validators for specific sections of the HEI's CC SO THAT they can do their tasks in a controlled way
- AS AN editor I WANT to edit data in a certain section of the HEI's CC SO THAT such data can be available for the CC
- AS AN editor I WANT to load information from an existing source SO THAT they can populate easily
- AS A validator I WANT to validate the data included in HEI's CCs SO THAT it is right for publication
- AS A HEI administrator I WANT to manage versions of a HEI CC SO THAT they are properly available and updated.
- AS A HEI administrator/Programme administrator/Editor I WANT load all the information from a previous exported section of a file (Excel, Word) SO THAT I can populate the information easier

- AS A HEI administrator/Programme administrator/Editor WANT save all the information available in a section SO THAT I can work with it offline and save for backup
- AS A HEI administrator I WANT to be able to define a calendar (agenda) and establish important dates for CC population and validation SO THAT the CC can be available and published at a proper time
- AS A non-authenticated user I WANT to report on missing data, inconsistencies and inaccuracies SO THAT the CC can be improved
- As A non-authenticated (local) Student I WANT to identify the possible host institutions where I can go (the ones that have a IIA with my home institution) SO THAT I can find the possible destinations in a better way
- AS A Student I WANT to see the ratings made by previous students for a certain programme/subject SO THAT I can take better decisions about my stay
- I WANT to load the information available in the Institutions/organizational units available in EWP APIs SO THAT I do not have to upload it again and I do not make any mistake.
- As A HEI Administrator I WANT to be able to send notifications to all the staff in charge of the population and validation of CC information SO THAT I can ensure the work is finished on time.

2.4. Required functionality

- User management
 - Authentication
 - User registration and authentication
 - Preferably using an IdP, SSO
 - Ideally automatic, no user moderation or manual interaction
 - Authorization
 - Handle administrator access
 - Handle authorization according to user role in HEI
 - Control the ability to create, update, delete or view data
 - Control the ability to manage other users
- Data storage:
 - Data model: Plan and create a database model that stores data
 - Data storage: Store course and related data in a commonly used database type
- Data edition
 - Edit text fields
 - Edit fields based on vocabularies, taxonomies
 - Multilanguage support
- Data validation
 - Ensuring data standard compliance
 - Ensuring data imported or entered is valid
- Data migration (bulk data creation)
 - import from a commonly used source format (using a spreadsheet in CSV format)
 - Ideally handle recurring imports with change management
 - Creating data in the database (if input is valid) via POSTing to an API
- CRUD operation (non-bulk)
 - Creating, updating data through the application UI, optionally using an API
 - Displaying data through the UI and exposing it via API endpoints
 - Deleting data (ideally keeping historical storage)
- Version management
 - Creating a new version of the CC
 - Managing the state of versions. Possible states are: Created, Manageable (Available for Management by Administrators), Editable (Available for Edition), Validable (Available for Validation), Validated, Published-Official, Published-Non-official, UnPublished.

- Manage a version state calendar.
 - Browse versions
 - Check version consistency
- Instance management
 - Creating new instances for specific entities in the CC.
 - Assigning new instances to users
- Browse
 - Navigate through HEIs
 - Navigate through the HEIs entities
- Search
 - Find specific topics in the CC
 - Find specific services in the CC
- Report
 - Inform about outdated information, inappropriate content, inconsistencies
 - Provide feedback about the CC

2.5. Non-Functional Requirements

- Open-source software.
- To be installable on premises
- To be installable in the cloud
- Multilingualism
- Responsive
- Accessible
- Usability and user experience
- Accurate information
- Interoperable (machine-readable)

3. Hardware and software components

3.1. High-Level Architecture Diagram(s)

Figure 1 shows a high-level architecture diagram of the eventual DACEM CC solution. This is strongly based in the EWP network as described in report 2.2 (activity 2.4). In colour three different kind of HEI entities are represented: an individual university in blue, an individual Polytechnic institute in green, a EUA in yellow. Each one of these entities has its own installation of the CC. In the case of the EUA it can be seen as it is composed by several HEIs, but they all share the same CC installation. In addition, the three HEI entities may have available different implementations of EWP APIS.

The figure is completed with three key components represented in the top area:

- The EWP registry is a central component of the EWP network. It acts as a directory where the services (APIs) provided by different institutions are published. This facilitates to third parties the location of services provided by a certain institution. The CC installations could be published in this registry, also.
- The User Authentication service will provide authentication for the users that can be involved in the CC administration and management. MyAcademicID is already available with users from most European HEIs.
- The DACEM CC (cloud) represents an installation of a CC for those institutions that do not want to install the CC in their own premises.

Figure 1. Representation of the DACEM high level view

3.2. System requirements

As most web applications, the system constitutes of servers and clients. To deploy the application to the servers, the following software requirements should be met.

3.2.1. Application server

Operating system requirements

There is no strict operating system requirement on the server side for the application, though it should support running the required web server software. A free Linux distribution is recommended due to its stability, security, and compatibility with the chosen technology stack, including PHP, MariaDB, and Drupal. Linux also provides robust performance for web hosting environments and is widely supported by most cloud providers.

Software requirements

Role	Name	Version
Web server (one of the listed)	Apache	2.4.7+
	Nginx	1.1+
Programming language	PHP	8.3

3.2.2. Database Server

Software requirements

Co-financed by the European Union. The opinions and views expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor those of the Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (SEPIE). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Role	Name	Version
Database	MariaDB	10.6+

In case a replicated database is needed, in case the amount of information is too large, a solution involving the MariaDB Galera Cluster¹ could be provided. Replication is a feature allowing the contents of one or more primary servers to be mirrored on one or more replica servers. This can be needed in order to improve the scalability and performance of the solution.

3.2.3. Clients

Browser requirements

- The latest release of each of the latest two supported major versions of:
 - Desktop browsers: Google Chrome, Firefox, Safari, Microsoft Edge, Opera
 - Mobile browsers: Safari for iOS
- The latest supported release of the latest major version of:
 - Desktop browsers: Firefox ESR
 - Mobile browsers: Chrome for Android, Chrome for iOS, Opera Mini (except for 'extreme data savings' mode), Samsung Internet

3.3. Environments

- Local development environment – For development
- Development server – For development using services unavailable from a local environment
- Staging server – For Quality Assurance (QA) and acceptance testing purposes
- Production server
 - On-premise
 - Platform

3.4. Software components

- General considerations for choosing a stack
 - Free and open source
 - Cost effective and easy to host
 - CMS features are necessary (User management, Content management, ...)
 - Extensibility
 - Has extensible built-in tools to expose APIs and is extensible to expose data in different data standards
- Regularly maintained (bug fixes and security patches)

3.4.1. Programming languages and frameworks

- PHP
- JavaScript
- Bootstrap

¹ <https://mariadb.com/kb/en/using-mariadb-replication-with-mariadb-galera-cluster-using-mariadb-replica/>

3.4.2. Tools

- Git and GitHub
- Composer
- Docker
- ddev

3.4.3. Drupal

Considering the previous requirements, the CC will be supported by Drupal 10.

Drupal is chosen because it provides the most flexibility for customization:

- The main functionality of the CC will be covered by Drupal Core CMS features.
- Extensibility will be supported by Drupal components.
- Configuration management and recipes will be used to support the deployment
- Drupal deployment and software distribution strategies

Drupal architecture is more a set of interlinked components than a structured hierarchy. It consists of a core APIs, modules, and themes. A key feature for DACEM is its support for multi-site environments. This enables different web properties appear to be separate sites but actually share common Drupal components. In this way, different HEIs might be deployed with some differences in the same CC installation, so that each HEI can tailor its own theme, content and functionality.

3.4.3.1. Drupal APIs

At the heart of Drupal is a set of API services, (see Figure 2 in blue) that are used by modules to interact with content and with other modules. Drupal's modules sit on top of these API services.

Figure 2. Drupal Architecture by John VanDyk

The core APIs of Drupal consist of:

- Batch processing
- File Storage
- Menu
- Theming (rendering)
- Caching
- Forms & processing
- Modules
- Unicode utilities
- Database abstraction
- Image manipulation
- Output filtering
- Update system
- Email handling
- Locale & language
- Session Handling
- XMLRPC

Some of the APIs worth highlighting:

- Caching API. This improves response time by storing the output of a page so that Drupal doesn't need to render it again each time there is a page request.
- Database Abstraction API. This shields the developer from having to work directly with database systems. As long as someone has written a driver that allows Drupal to interface with a particular database, this API allows you to make database queries, update and delete tables.
- Menu API. Menu API does the heavy work of routing. Whenever a web page is required, Menu API determines what's needed to build that page. It checks that the client has permission to access the path, invokes the first module needed to render the page, and if all goes well, Menu API eventually delivers a rendered page to the client. A module might contain hooks ("events") that bring other modules into play but in the end, it's the Menu API that delivers the result.
- Modules API. Handles loading of Drupal modules, including creating events so that other modules required for building the page know to spring into action.
- Session Handling API. This authenticates and then keeps track of users who are logged in through unique session IDs. This lets processes work with session information.
- Themeing API (Rendering). Just what it sounds like – controls the presentation of content from Drupal. This handles requests for themed output, taking raw data and applying the correct layout for the page, and sends back to the Menu API.

3.4.3.2. Drupal modules

A Drupal module consists of code and files that extend Drupal's functionality. Modules make use of Drupal's APIs and are event-driven: they 'listen' for hooks, or events, generated by APIs and other modules which will trigger them into action.

Some modules are essential to Drupal operations. These are part of the standard Drupal release which is maintained by the Drupal development team, and known collectively as Core Modules.

Other modules are contributed modules which developers can add and enable for their installation. Architecturally there's no difference between contributed modules and core modules; they all make use of standard Drupal APIs.

The writing of new Drupal should be done following some documented best practices.

The Drupal community provides a large set of contributed modules that are provided for free or premium.

The following modules are considered for DACEM:

- Core modules used by the application that are not activated by the default Drupal installation
 - Serialization
 - RESTful Web Services
 - JSON:API
- Contributed modules used by the application
 - OpenIDConnect for MyAcademicID integration
 - EUF modules for entity data models and integration with existing tools and data sources like the HEI API
- Modules developed for DACEM application specific purposes
 - Serialization / Deserialization modules (OCCAPI, EWP)
 - Access control
 - Modules supporting Editorial Workflows
 - Modules supporting versioning

4. Data model

The DACEM data model involves the entities shown in Figure 3. These entities have been proposed based on the results of WP2. Particularly, it has been taking into account the existing specifications and standards related to CC and some issues identified in the interviews and surveys maintained with students and HEIs staff. Next items show the main source of the information entities:

- Yellow entities have been taken from the “ECTS Users’ Guide 2015”. They refer to General Information, Resources and Services, Program (Joint Programme) and Individual Educational Component (IEC). They represent the basic information that should be kept in a Erasmus+ CC. Many people is confused regarding the inclusion of General Information and Resources and Services entities, but it is a demand of the Erasmus+ programme.
- Green entities appear in several main specifications: OCCAPI, OOAPI or EWP. They include information that can be also useful for end-users, specifically students. For example, the instance entity refers to the running version of a IEC (or programme) that changes every academic year. For example: init and finish dates, schedule, responsible teacher, assessment dates, assessment procedures, etc. We consider a similar instance entity can be also required for programmes involving the set of IEC instances. Organizational Unit and Academic Term involve key information that should also appear in the CC.
- Pink entities represent information that was demanded by end-users. For example, some users complained about the differences between the institution location and the campus location. This may mean a great difference in some cases. Similarly, EUAs demanded for visibility of alliance joint programmes and initiatives in the CC.
- Other entities, in gray, were included to provide an homogeneous management of common issues.

Figure 3. DACEM data model main entities

5. Interoperability with external systems

5.1. High-level interoperability diagram

5.2. Integrations

Integrations with the following systems should be provided:

- MyAcademicID for Single Sign-On. This should provide basic user data and essential affiliation data, needed for editorial purposes and access control on multi-HEI deployments and should also streamline user creation and data management.
- HEIAPI for importing up-to-date Institution data. Using a central, up-to-date repository for HEI data should ensure consistency of information across different CC application instances.

5.3. Interfaces

Interfaces with the following systems should be supported:

- OLA (via API using OCCAPI DDS). Providing a machine-readable format, that the OLA platform will be able to interpret should enable the external system to use reliable course data provided by the DACEM application, help OLA users to minimize problems originating from manual entry and ultimately streamline OLA creation.

- EWP (via API using EWP Course DDS). Same applies to interfacing with the EWP network. The goal for the application is to provide output through APIs, that conform with the EWP data standard, thereby enabling systems capable of handling this data format to leverage the information stored in the application.